

TRIGONOMETRIK VAZNLII OPTIMAL KVADRATUR FORMULALARNI KOMPYUTER TOMOGRAFIYASI TASVIRLARINI QAYTA TIKLASHGA TATBIQI

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Annotatsiya: Trigonometrik vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalar Fure koeffitsientlarini hisoblashda, geometriya, yadro fizikasi, signallarni qayta ishlash, kompyuter tomografiyasi va boshqa ko'plab amaliy masalalarda uchragan trigonometrik vaznli integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun tatbiq etish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: kubatur formulalar, kvadratur formulalar, xatolik funksionali, xatolik funksionali normasi, optimal koeffitsiyentlar, Fure integrallari.

Kirish. Ushbu ishda trigonometrik vaznli integrallarini taqribiy hisoblash uchun qurilgan

$$\int_0^1 \sin(2\pi\omega x)\varphi(x)dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_s[\beta]\varphi[\beta] \quad (1)$$

va

$$\int_0^1 \cos(2\pi\omega x)\varphi(x)dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_c[\beta]\varphi[\beta] \quad (2)$$

optimal kvadratur formulalarni kompyuter tomografiyasi tasvirlari filtrlab orqaga proektsiyalash usuli yordamida qayta tiklashga qo'llanilishini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Bizga ma'lumki, signallarni tahlil qilish va tasvirlarni qayta ishlash kabi amaliy masalalar Fure integrallarini hisoblashga olib kelinadi. Masalan Radon almashtirishi bilan kompyuter tomografiyasida tasvirlarni qayta tiklash masalasini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Bunda $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ bo'lganda quyidagi ko'rinishdagi

$$I(\varphi) = \int_0^1 e^{2\pi i\omega x} \varphi(x)dx \quad (3)$$

integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash talab etiladi. Bu turdagi integrallarda kuchli tebranuvchi funksiyalarning integrallarini har doim ham aniq qiymatini topib bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun, ularni taqribiy hisoblash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Taqribiy hisoblashning standart usullari doimo yaxshi natija bermaydi. Demak, kuchli tebranuvchi funksiyalarning integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun maxsus metodlar

ishlab chiqish talab etiladi. Birinchi bo'lib, Faylon 1928 yili effektiv hisoblash usulini taqdim etgan. Keyingi yillarda kuchli tebranuvchi funksiyalarni integrallarini hisoblashni boshqa turli usullari rivojlandi. Masalan Faylon usuliga asoslangan usullar, Klenshov-Kurtis-Faylon usuli, Levin usuli, asimtotik yoyish usuli. Oxirgi yillarda $L_2^{(m)}$ va $W_2^{(m,m-1)}$ Gilbert fazolarida $\omega \in \mathbb{Z}$ qiymatlarida X.M.Shadimetov, G.V.Milovanovich, A.R.Hayotov va N.D.Boltaevlar Fure koeffitsientlarini hisoblash uchun optimal kvadratur formulalar qurish bo'yicha ilmiy izlanishlar olib borishgan [7,9]. Sobolevning $L_2^{(m)}[0,1]$ fazosida (3) ko'rinishidagi integral uchun ushbu

$$\int_0^1 e^{2\pi i\omega x} \varphi(x)dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C[\beta]\varphi[\beta] \quad (4)$$

optimal kvadratur formula Ch.-O.Li, S.Jeon, X.M.Shadimetov, A.R.Hayotovlarning ishlarida qurilgan [8]. Bu kvadratur formulaning Sard ma'nosidagi koeffitsientlari uchun quyida trigonometrik vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalarning koeffitsiyentlari nomli bo'limida tasdiq berilgan.

Trigonometrik vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalarning koeffitsiyentlari.

Ma'lumki $e^{2\pi i\omega x}$ vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalar uchun ushbu teoremani keltiramiz. Bu teorema [8] ishda keltirilgan va isbotlangan.

Teorema 1. Sobolevning $L_2^{(m)}[0,1]$ fazosida $N+1 \geq m$ bo'lganda va barcha haqiqiy ω va $\omega h \notin \mathbb{Z}$ qiymatlar uchun (4) optimal kvadratur formulaning koeffitsientlari quyidagicha

$$C[0] = h \left(\frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h} K_{\omega, m}}{e^{2\pi i \omega h} - 1} - \frac{1}{2\pi i \omega h} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \left(a_k \frac{q_k}{q_k - 1} + b_k \frac{q_k^N}{1 - q_k} \right) \right),$$

$$C[\beta] = h \left(e^{2\pi i \omega h \beta} K_{\omega, m} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} (a_k q_k^\beta + b_k q_k^{N-\beta}) \right), \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1,$$

$$C[N] = h \left(\frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h} K_{\omega, m}}{1 - e^{2\pi i \omega h}} + \frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{2\pi i \omega h} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \left(a_k \frac{q_k^N}{1 - q_k} + b_k \frac{q_k}{q_k - 1} \right) \right),$$

bu yerda a_k va b_k lar quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasidan aniqlanadi

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} a_k \left[\sum_{t=1}^j \frac{q_k \Delta^t 0^j}{(q_k - 1)^{t+1}} \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} b_k \left[\sum_{t=1}^j \frac{q_k^{N+t} \Delta^t 0^j}{(1 - q_k)^{t+1}} \right]$$

$$= \frac{j!}{(2\pi i \omega h)^{j+1}} - \sum_{t=1}^j \frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h} K_{\omega, m} \Delta^t 0^j}{(e^{2\pi i \omega h} - 1)^{t+1}}, j = 1, 2, \dots, m-1,$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} a_k \left[\sum_{t=1}^j \frac{q_k^t \Delta^t 0^j}{(1 - q_k)^{t+1}} - \sum_{\alpha=1}^j h^{\alpha-j} \binom{j}{\alpha} \sum_{t=1}^{\alpha} \frac{q_k^{N+t} \Delta^t 0^\alpha}{(1 - q_k)^{t+1}} \right]$$

$$+ \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} b_k \left[\sum_{t=1}^j \frac{q_k^{N+1} \Delta^t 0^j}{(q_k - 1)^{t+1}} - \sum_{\alpha=1}^j h^{\alpha-j} \binom{j}{\alpha} \sum_{t=1}^{\alpha} \frac{q_k \Delta^t 0^\alpha}{(q_k - 1)^{t+1}} \right]$$

$$= \frac{(-1)^{j+1} j!}{(2\pi i \omega h)^{j+1}} + \sum_{\alpha=1}^j h^{\alpha-j} \frac{(-1)^\alpha j! e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{(j - \alpha)! (2\pi i \omega h)^{\alpha+1}} - \frac{K_{\omega, m}}{1 - e^{2\pi i \omega h}} \sum_{t=1}^j \left(\frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{1 - e^{2\pi i \omega h}} \right)^t \Delta^t 0^j$$

$$+ \frac{K_{\omega, m} e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{1 - e^{2\pi i \omega h}} \sum_{\alpha=1}^j h^{\alpha-j} \binom{j}{\alpha} \sum_{t=1}^{\alpha} \left(\frac{e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{1 - e^{2\pi i \omega h}} \right)^t \Delta^t 0^\alpha, j = 1, 2, \dots, m-1,$$

q_k lar $E_{2m-2}(x)$ Eylar-Frobenius

ko'pxadining ildizlari, $|q_k| < 1$ va

$$K_{\omega, m} = \left(\frac{\sin \pi \omega h}{\pi \omega h} \right)^{2m} \frac{(2m-1)!}{2 \sum_{\alpha=0}^{m-2} a_\alpha \cos[2\pi \omega h(m-1-\alpha)] + a_{m-1}}.$$

$$a_\alpha = \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha} (-1)^j \binom{2m}{j} (s+1-j)^{2m-1}$$

Bu yerda

lar $2m-2$ -darajali $E_{2m-2}(x)$ Eylar-Frobenius ko'phadining koeffitsientlari.

Shu bilan birga qurilgan (4) optimal kvadratur formula kompyuter tomografiyasi tasvirlarini qayta tiklashga qo'llanilgan [8].

Biz [1-6] ishlarda keltirilgan $\sin(2\pi \omega x)$ va $\cos(2\pi \omega x)$ vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalarning koeffitsientlari uchun quyidagi tasdiqlarni eslatib o'tamiz.

Teorema 2. Sobolevning $L_2^{(m)}(0,1)$ fazosida (1) ko'rinishdagi Sard ma'nosida optimal kvadratur formulaning, $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ va $\omega \notin \mathbb{Z}$ bo'lganda, koeffitsientlari uchun quyidagi tengliklar o'rinli

$$C_s[0] = h \left[\frac{1}{2\pi \omega h} - K_{m, \omega} \frac{\cos(\pi \omega h)}{2 \sin(\pi \omega h)} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{s,k} q_k - n_{s,k} q_k^N}{q_k - 1} \right],$$

$$C_s[\beta] = h \left[K_{m, \omega} \sin(2\pi \omega [\beta]) + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} (m_{s,k} q_k^\beta + n_{s,k} q_k^{N-\beta}) \right], \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1,$$

$$C_s[N] = h \left[-\frac{\cos(2\pi \omega)}{2\pi \omega h} + K_{m, \omega} \frac{\cos(2\pi \omega - \pi \omega h)}{2 \sin(\pi \omega h)} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{-m_{s,k} q_k^N + n_{s,k} q_k}{q_k - 1} \right],$$

bu yerda $[\beta] = h\beta$, q_k lar $(2m-2)$ - darajali Eylar - Frobenius ko'phadi $E_{2m-2}(x)$ ning $|q_k| < 1$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi ildizlari,

$$K_{m, \omega} = \frac{(2 - 2\cos(2\pi \omega h))^m \cdot (2m-1)! \cdot (-1)^m}{(2\pi \omega h)^{2m} \left(2 \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} a_{k, 2m-2} \cos(2\pi \omega h(m-1-k)) + a_{m-1, 2m-2} \right)},$$

$a_{k, 2m-2}$ lar $E_{2m-2}(x)$ ko'phadining koeffitsientlari, $m_{s,k}$ va $n_{s,k}$ lar quyidagi chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasidan aniqlanadi

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{s,k} q_k - (-1)^j n_{s,k} q_k^{N+1}}{(q_k - 1)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(q_k) = -\frac{(-1)^j j! \cos(\frac{\pi j}{2})}{(2\pi \omega h)^{j+1}} -$$

$$-\frac{(1 + (-1)^j) K_{m, \omega} e^{2\pi i \omega h}}{2i(e^{2\pi i \omega h} - 1)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(e^{2\pi i \omega h}), j = 1, 2, \dots, m-1,$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{s,k} q_k^{N+1} - (-1)^j n_{s,k} q_k}{(1-q_k)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(q_k) = \frac{j! \cos(2\pi\omega + \frac{\pi j}{2})}{(2\pi\omega h)^{j+1}} - \frac{(e^{2\pi i\omega} + (-1)^j e^{-2\pi i\omega}) K_{m,\omega} e^{2\pi i\omega h}}{2i(1-e^{2\pi i\omega h})^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(e^{2\pi i\omega h}), j=1,2,\dots,m-1.$$

Teorema 3. Sobolevning $L_2^{(m)}(0,1)$ fazosida (2) ko'rinishdagi Sard ma'nosida optimal kvadratur formulaning, $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ va $\omega \notin \mathbb{Z}$ bo'lganda, koeffitsientlar uchun quyidagi tengliklar o'rinli

$$\overset{\circ}{C}_c[0] = h \left[\frac{K_{m,\omega}}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{c,k} q_k - n_{c,k} q_k^N}{q_k - 1} \right],$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}_c[\beta] = h \left[K_{m,\omega} \cos(2\pi\omega[\beta]) + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} (m_{c,k} q_k^\beta + n_{c,k} q_k^{N-\beta}) \right], \beta=1,2,\dots,N-1,$$

$$\overset{\circ}{C}_c[N] = h \left[\frac{\sin(2\pi\omega)}{2\pi\omega h} - \frac{K_{m,\omega} \sin(2\pi\omega - \pi\omega h)}{2 \sin(\pi\omega h)} + \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{-m_{c,k} q_k^N + n_{c,k} q_k}{q_k - 1} \right]$$

bu yerda $[\beta] = h\beta$, q_k lar $(2m-2)$ – darajali Eylar – Frobenius ko'phadi $E_{2m-2}(x)$ ning $|q_k| < 1$ shartni qanoatlantiruvchi ildizlari,

$$K_{m,\omega} = \frac{(-1)^m (2m-1)! (e^{2\pi i\omega h} - 1)^{2m}}{(2\pi\omega h)^{2m} e^{2\pi i\omega h} E_{2m-2}(e^{2\pi i\omega h})},$$

$a_{k,2m-2}$ lar $E_{2m-2}(x)$ ko'phad koeffitsientlari, $m_{c,k}$ va $n_{c,k}$ lar quyidagi chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasidan aniqlanadi

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{c,k} q_k - (-1)^j n_{c,k} q_k^{N+1}}{(q_k - 1)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(q_k) = \frac{(-1)^j j! \sin(\frac{\pi j}{2})}{(2\pi\omega h)^{j+1}} - \frac{(1 - (-1)^j) K_{m,\omega} e^{2\pi i\omega h}}{2(e^{2\pi i\omega h} - 1)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(e^{2\pi i\omega h}), j=1,2,\dots,m-1,$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \frac{m_{c,k} q_k^{N+1} - (-1)^j n_{c,k} q_k}{(1-q_k)^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(q_k) = -\frac{j! \sin(2\pi\omega + \frac{\pi j}{2})}{(2\pi\omega h)^{j+1}} - \frac{(e^{2\pi i\omega} - (-1)^j e^{-2\pi i\omega}) K_{m,\omega} e^{2\pi i\omega h}}{2i(1-e^{2\pi i\omega h})^{j+1}} E_{j-1}(e^{2\pi i\omega h}), j=1,2,\dots,m-1.$$

Sobolev fazosida Sard ma'nosida optimal kvadratur formulalar qurish va xatoliklarini baholash bilan ushbu [1-12] ishlarda ham tanishish mumkin.

Shu bilan birga yuqorida qurilgan optimal kvadratur formulalar yordamida kompyuter tomografiyasiga tadbirlarini qarab chiqamiz.

Kompyuter tomografiyasiga tadbiri.

Yuqorida berilgan Teorema 2 va Teorema 3 lardan Teorema 1 ni koeffitsientlarini kelib chiqishini ko'rish qiyin emas. Ya'ni,

$$C[0] = C_c[0] + iC_s[0],$$

$$C[\beta] = C_c[\beta] + iC_s[\beta], \beta=1,2,\dots,N-1,$$

$$C[N] = C_c[N] + iC_s[N].$$

Bundan tashqari Teorema 1 da keltirilgan a_k va b_k lar uchun olingan tenglamalar sistemasini ham yuqoridagi Teorema 2 va Teorema 3 larda aniqlangan $m_{s,k}$, $n_{s,k}$, $m_{c,k}$ va $n_{c,k}$ lar uchun olingan tenglamalar sistemalaridan kelib chiqishini ko'rish mumkin.

Kompyuter tomografiyasida tasvirlarni qayta tiklash uchun quyidagi algoritm berilgan.

1. $P(t_m, \theta_k)$ sinogrammaning diskret shakli $t_m \in [a, b], \theta \in [0, \pi]$ lar uchun berilgan.

2. Taklif etilgan optimal kvadratur formula yordamida Fure koeffitsientlarini hisoblash:

$$S(\omega, \theta) \cong S(\omega, \theta_k) = \sum_{m=0}^M \overset{\circ}{C}_{m,-\omega} P(t_m, \theta_k), \omega \in \mathbb{R}.$$

3. Taklif etilgan kvadratur formula yordamida teskari Fure almashtirishlarining koeffitsientlarini hisoblash:

$$Q(t, \theta) \cong Q(t, \theta_k) = \sum_{n=0}^N \overset{\circ}{C}_{n,t} S(\omega_n, \theta_k) | \omega_n |.$$

4. KT da orqaga proeksiyalash usuli bilan tasvirlarni qayta tiklash:

$$f(x, y) = \int_0^\pi Q(t, \theta) d\theta \cong \frac{\pi}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} Q(t, \theta_k).$$

Rasm 1. Chapda fft va ifft dan foydalanib FBP yordamida, ikkinchi tartibli optimal kvadratur formula bilan (o‘rtada) va uchinchi tartibli kvadratur formula bilan (o‘ngda) tasvirlarni qayta tiklash natijalari barilgan.

	Shepp-Logan without noise			Shepp-Logan with noise		
	conv-FBP fft and ifft	OQF m = 2	OQF m = 3	conv-FBP fft and ifft	OQF m = 2	OQF m = 3
E_{max}	0.3458	0.3526	0.3307	0.3722	0.3634	0.3472
MSE	7.9648e-04	7.2111e-04	6.5084e-04	7.9088e-04	7.4509e-04	6.4990e-04
PSNR	30.9883	31.4200	31.8652	31.0189	31.2779	31.8715

Jadval 1. Yuqoridagi rasm 1 da berilgan KT da tasvirlarni qayta tiklashning sonli natijalari.

Xulosa

Qurilgan trigonometrik vaznli optimal kvadratur formulalar yordamida kompyuter tomografiyasida tasvirlarni qayta tiklash masalasi uchun tatbiq etildi. Yuqoridagi (4) optimal kvadratur formulaning $m=2$ bo‘lgandagi hol uchun olingan optimal kvadratur formulalar bilan kompyuter tomografiyasida Shepp – Logan tasvirlarni qayta tiklab, FBP usulida olingan natijalar bilan taqqoslandi va olingan natijalarda tasvir aniqligi yaxshilangan ekanligi ko‘rsatildi.

Minnatdorchilik

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